

CARDIOVASCULAR RISK IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Introduction: It has been proven that rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is an autoimmune, immunoinflammatory rheumatic disease characterized by chronic erosive arthritis and systemic damage to internal organs, leading to early disability and shortening the life expectancy of patients. The prevalence of RA among the adult population in different geographic zones of the world ranges from 0.5 to 2%. Rheumatoid arthritis significantly reduces the life expectancy of patients due to the development of early atherothrombosis, arterial hypertension and associated vascular complications. The main cause of death in RA is cardiovascular diseases, and the main causes of high mortality from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) in RA are the rapid progression of atherosclerosis and the development of heart failure.

Aim: To assess the level of cardiovascular risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis.

Materials and methods: 60 patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) were examined (ACR / EULAR criteria 2010), women - 43 (71.6%) and men - 17 (28.3%). The patients' age ranged from 36 to 60 years, on average 46 ± 5.7 years, the duration of the disease ranged from 4 to 15 years, on average 7.3 ± 3.4 years. Cardiovascular risk stratification was performed using the SCORE / EULAR scale. The patients underwent: OAC, OAM, rheumatic test, detection of ACCP in the blood, determination of total blood cholesterol, fasting blood glucose, ECG, Echo-KG, R-graphy of the hands, ultrasound of internal organs.

Results: In 72% of patients, ACCP was detected, in 70% - seropositive RA, in 30% - seronegative. In 24 (40%) patients, grade III RA activity was detected, in

33 (55%) patients, stage III-IV RA was radiologically determined. Clinical examination revealed the presence of the following risk factors in patients: obesity (body mass index (BMI) ≥ 30 kg/m²) was observed in 22 (37%) patients, smoking - in 9 (15%), physical inactivity - in 18 (30%), hypercholesterolemia - in 27 (45%), burdened heredity for cardiovascular diseases - in 21 (35%). Hypercholesterolemia in RA is associated with inflammatory markers: C-reactive protein (CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), rheumatoid factor. 12 (20%) patients were diagnosed with coronary artery disease (IHD), 7 of them were established earlier (before the onset of RA), in 5 - IHD was diagnosed for the first time. Arterial hypertension was detected in 16 (27%) patients. Chronic heart failure (CHF) FC II-III according to NYHA was diagnosed in 5 (17%) patients out of 32, in 3 cases with preserved left ventricular ejection fraction (LV). In 3 patients, CHF was caused by IHD, in 8 - IHD and AH. Fasting hyperglycemia was detected in 12 (20%) patients. Anemia of varying severity was detected in 46 (77%) patients. When conducting an ECG in patients, changes were revealed in the form: metabolic changes in the ventricular myocardium - in 31 (52.5%) patients, left ventricular hypertrophy.

Conclusions: Thus, the majority of patients with identified ACCP and positive for RF with a high degree of disease activity have the highest cardiovascular risk. This is due to an increase in the frequency of traditional risk factors and clinical manifestations of cardiovascular diseases. In addition to detecting and monitoring RA activity, it is necessary to change the lifestyle of patients, as well as timely detection and treatment of comorbid conditions.

